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D3.2 Training Package: FAIR Chemistry Cookbook

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
CIF	Crystallographic Information File
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
InChI	IUPAC International Chemical Identifier
IUPAC	International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry
JB	Jupyter Book
JN	Jupyter Notebook
NFDI4Chem	Nationale Forschungsdaten Infrastruktur, Chemistry Consortium
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology (U.S.)
NLM	National Library of Medicine (U.S.)
OPSIN	Open Parser for Systematic IUPAC Nomenclature
PARC	Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemical
PR	Pull Request (GitHub)
PSDI	Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure
RIPE	Reliable, Interpretable, Processable, Exchangeable
W3ID	World Wide Web Permanent Identifier
WP03	WorldFAIR Chemistry Work Package

Executive summary

The International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) has initiated a community project through the WorldFAIR Project to develop an online community resource of practical and re-usable training materials that demonstrate how to manage digital data files and content. The overall goal is to get practical tools and tips in the hands of practising chemists to lower barriers and smooth the adoption of best practices for sharing and re-using FAIR chemical data.

The purpose of this deliverable is to develop a digital web resource that will support various user groups in the chemical sciences and allied fields with training in the FAIR principles and machine-readable chemical data. This 'Cookbook' serves as a toolbox of interactive recipes for implementing FAIR at various levels and for various user experience levels, ranging from educators who need demonstration resources for instruction, to students who learn by doing, to practitioners who need a quick orientation on a tool or resource.

This Cookbook is envisioned to serve a variety of users across a wide range of scientific domains and sectors. We anticipate that commercial, academic, and educational institutions will benefit. Researchers and development units, including scientists incorporating machine learning into their research and librarians supporting researchers will find this resource especially helpful. The Cookbook's broad applicability will be extremely helpful to journal editors, repository curators, systems and software developers, and anyone else handling chemical data.

This report describes an online cookbook platform that can be readily accessed with broadly available online infrastructure and exemplifies the FAIR principles and best practices in cheminformatics. Developing a sustainable infrastructure that invites practical contributions from chemists, data scientists, educators, and students worldwide enables IUPAC to leverage the collective expertise of the community in best practices for managing and reusing chemical data.

The overarching goal of the WorldFAIR Chemistry Work Package (WP03) is to support the use of chemical data standards in research and curation workflows and to enable downstream data reuse through provision of practical direction and resources. Other deliverables developed under the WorldFAIR Chemistry (WP03) case study include a framework that can be used by policymakers and developers of services and tools to support FAIR reporting of chemical data (D3.1 Digital guidance), and a specification for a shared data model for chemical information exchange (D3.3 Utility Services for Chemistry Standards).

WP03 activities are coordinated through IUPAC, the world authority on chemical nomenclature and terminology that constitute a common global language for communicating chemistry. In the context of the formal IUPAC process for reviewing and adopting consensus standards in chemistry, this work should be regarded as provisional guidance. Complete review and adoption of standards through IUPAC to reach the status of "Recommendation," which has a specific meaning in the IUPAC lexicon, will occur after WP03 is complete. The IUPAC WorldFAIR project thanks all contributors to the original Cookbook project, listed in Appendix 8.1.

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1. Introduction

Students and practitioners of chemistry alike work in a scientific domain where digital data is becoming a fundamental part of their job. However, the principles of FAIR—Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability¹—are not yet deeply ingrained in the collective consciousness of the chemistry domain, representing a significant disconnect between traditional chemical education and the demands of modern research methodologies. For the field to remain attractive to future talent, we will need a transition to using the latest digital tools. This cannot happen with the current state of teaching and lack of understanding of FAIR data, digital data management, cheminformatics and data science.

Traditionally chemists have captured chemical data in hardcopy laboratory notebooks. Much of their training revolves around proper documentation of their process in these resources. In more recent years, the focus has been on storing files on local computers (or the computer running the laboratory instrument) but has evolved little past this. In many situations, data published with papers are sparse and not provided in open, FAIR formats. There is a significant need to not only make the FAIR principles widely known and understood in chemistry, but also to provide chemistry related examples of how and why these principles should be integrated into research practice as data workflows transition online.²

Increasing amounts of chemical data are becoming openly available for querying directly via the cloud. Many chemistry data resources provide web services to programmatically query and retrieve data for particular chemicals or properties. Familiarity with techniques for digitally representing chemical structures and other data components will allow researchers to tap into multiple networked resources for searching and analysis, as well as enable their own data to be more discoverable. Proficiency in basic digital data handling skills can empower researchers to exploit FAIR and open resources and handle real-world chemical data scenarios more effectively through cheminformatics and data science techniques.

With this project, we aim to create a repository of interactive tutorials that provide hands-on experience with digital data sources, tools and workflows pertaining to automated chemical data processing. Digital notebooks with executable code blocks allow users to engage directly with basic cheminformatics functions integral to working with machine-readable data and enabling them to be FAIR. The goal is to provide the community with an accessible resource that exemplifies the FAIR principles and best practices in cheminformatics and showcases what can be done with this technology while enabling scientists to learn to utilise it.

¹ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² Herres-Pawlis, Sonja, et al. "Minimum Information Standards in Chemistry: A Call for Better Research Data Management Practices." *Angewandte Chemie International Edition* 61.51 (2022): e202203038. <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202203038>

This report describes an online ‘cookbook’ platform that can be readily accessed with broadly available online infrastructure. Developing a sustainable infrastructure that invites practical contributions from chemists, data scientists, educators, and students worldwide enables IUPAC to leverage the collective expertise of the community in best practices for managing and reusing chemical data in research, teaching and many broader applications including AI.

2. Training and skills in FAIR chemistry data

Chemistry underlies both living and materials systems. Chemical data is at the heart of data-driven discovery and innovation across the health and environmental science sectors and in many applied engineering fields. Preparing the chemical sciences to address broad-ranging data science problems will demand technical as well as scientific proficiencies: familiarity and skills in cheminformatics and data programming as well as research data management. As recognised in the biomedical community, training must foster development of scholars with expertise in both data science and expertise in a scientific domain as both are needed to develop and deploy usable and useful applications for harnessing data.³ Proficiencies in data analysis for any field will need to address core concepts of data standards, data management, data sharing and reproducibility in both manual and automated processes.

In a digital work environment, well-prepared researchers need to be comfortable working their way around digital data formats, code, and online computing platforms. This is especially critical for the next generation of scientists emerging into a world where integrity of innovation rests on integrity of data. Responsible data reuse by humans and machines begins with responsible data stewardship. Professionals of tomorrow will be increasingly involved in creating new ways to analyse, visualise, mine, and integrate data and information. Students of today need to learn how to extract meaning and insight from aggregations of data programmatically, to navigate the scale and range of data types and sources becoming available, and apply automated approaches to curation, dissemination, and analysis.

Emerging initiatives and recent studies in the chemical sciences show a domain ripe for scaling data methodologies but lacking in appropriate training to exploit the technologies. Basic curation processes for finding, retrieving, cleaning, transforming, and integrating data to be FAIR and reusable are significant but necessary time investments that could be more efficiently supported. Enabling data professionals and researchers to familiarise themselves with available tools and share approaches to common operations could enhance efficiency of research and innovation. This ecosystem hinges on improving the availability of consistently structured, well documented,

³ U. S. National Institutes of Health. A Platform for Biomedical Discovery and Data-Powered Health. National Library of Medicine Strategic Plan 2017–2027. https://www.nlm.nih.gov/pubs/plan/lrp17/NLM_StrategicReport2017_2027.html

machine-readable chemical data – research data that align with the FAIR data principles – and supporting researchers and stakeholders to implement and sustain these practices.^{4, 5, 6, 7}

2.1 Machine-readable chemistry data

FAIR-enabled data are structured and described to facilitate automated processing from machine to machine and system to system, thus being available for AI/ML and other digital applications. To be “fully AI-ready”, data structures need to be systematically organised and consistently formatted so that algorithms can parse and operate on them. Processable data structures need to adhere to discipline-specific data standards as well as be technically FAIR to ensure quality and accuracy of reuse. In this way, they become accessible through programmatic interfaces and can be tapped directly within user code for automated exchange and analysis.

These concepts as framed by the FAIR principles manifest as concrete technical attributes for programmers and data scientists in practice. They can be abstractions for those not familiar with navigating from an informatics / data structure perspective. To make sense of the applicability of the FAIR data principles in the context of machine-readability, it is important to appreciate how use cases for using chemical data can match with technical attributes that enable data to be reused through automated means. Different FAIR attributes (as supported by a FAIR-enabling resource or FER) enable specific functions that serve as a key to ‘unlock’ specific needs for reusability of a data object (i.e., a specific instance of data such as a file or record). For example, InChI supports a key function in this environment as a canonical structure-based identifier – any associated datasets where InChIs have been generated can be searched and verified by chemical structure and thus discoverable via federated searches and interoperable with other data resources.^{8, 9}

Representing chemical structures is one of the most critical functions in communicating chemistry. Machine-readability of chemical structures is a particularly significant issue in cheminformatics. Most chemical data resources are organised around chemical entities and many now provide programmatic interfaces (APIs), which allow users to query for a particular chemical through various web services. Automated access methods are often specific to individual resources and there are

⁴ Knight, N. J., Bicarregui, J., Montanari, B., Coles, S. J., Frey, J. G., Matthews, B., & Bunakov, V. (2023). Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure Phase 1 Pilot Report. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7684860>

⁵ U. S. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). Data Science for Undergraduates: Opportunities and Options. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/25104>

⁶ U. S. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2018). Data Science: Opportunities to Transform Chemical Sciences and Engineering. <https://nap.nationalacademies.org/catalog/25191>

⁷ Transform to Open Science (TOPS initiative), National Aeronautics and Space Administration. <https://nasa.github.io/Transform-to-Open-Science>

⁸ Goodman, J.M., Pletnev, I., Thiessen, P. et al. InChI version 1.06: now more than 99.99% reliable. J Cheminform 13, 40 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-021-00517-z>

⁹ McEwen, L., & Bruno, I. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D3.1) Digital recommendations for Chemistry FAIR data policy and practice (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887282>

varying approaches for representing chemical substance information depending on the scientific nature and context. While there are some common community-standard formats for chemical structures, different major chemical databases may interpret and process chemical structures differently and thus chemical interpretation can vary between data systems and directly impact downstream reuse. It is integral to the success of enabling, managing and working with FAIR chemical data to have a working understanding of the strengths and limitations of the commonly-used chemical notations and structure representations, the range of tools for translating between these, and tips on navigating different APIs available for chemical data resources.¹⁰

Representations of chemical transformations and expression of properties that can be consistently parsed and validated by machines are also important for processing chemical data in many areas of research. Documentation of data and uncertainties arising from measurement and analysis requires contextual parameters including conditions and methods for interpretation. Chemical data standards help ensure that data annotation is scientifically and technically **RIPE** – Reliable, Interpretable, Processable, Exchangeable – as well as FAIR-mature for meaningful data reuse. Learning to work with standard file formats such as CIF (chemical crystallography)¹¹, JCAMP-DX (various spectra types)¹² and mzML (mass spectra)¹³ can foster innovative informatics techniques that leverage the systematic description of data parameters.¹⁴ Citing standard chemistry concepts accessible via the IUPAC Gold Book¹⁵ to further annotate data can enrich data models and improve interoperability.¹⁶

2.2 Target audiences and stakeholders

User personas for chemical digital data training are diverse, encompassing individuals and teams on the cusp of embracing FAIR practices, requiring a resource like this Cookbook for skill enhancement in managing machine-readable data. It also caters to new entrants in FAIR-committed organisations who seek to self-train, and to those who might not be explicitly seeking FAIR-centric resources but discover that the Cookbook addresses their data management challenges. Additionally, the anticipated user base includes educators in the chemical sciences who are in search of targeted, structured teaching materials.

¹⁰ Thiessen, P., Bolton, E., Williams, A., McEwen, L. R., & Mustafa, F. (2023). WorldFAIR (D3.3) Utility services for Chemistry Standards (1.1). Zenodo. <https://10.5281/zenodo.10289785>

¹¹ <https://www.iucr.org/resources/cif>

¹² <https://iupac.org/what-we-do/digital-standards/jcamp-dx/>

¹³ Described in <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3073315/>

¹⁴ Lai, A., et al. "The next frontier of environmental unknowns: substances of unknown or variable composition, complex reaction products, or biological materials (UVCBs)." *Environmental Science & Technology* 56.12 (2022): 7448-7466. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.2c00321>

¹⁵ <https://goldbook.iupac.org/>

¹⁶ McEwen, L., & Bruno, I. (2023). WorldFAIR Project (D3.1) Digital recommendations for Chemistry FAIR data policy and practice (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7887282>

General categories of users include: practitioners for whom these skills are integral to their work; professionals who recognise the value that these skills add to their competencies; individuals driven by personal interest to learn more about FAIR chemistry; and educators who require comprehensive resources for instruction. The reach of the Cookbook extends across various scientific domains, likely resonating with professionals in Chemistry, Chemical Engineering, Materials, Biochemistry, and Pharmaceuticals, among others. The pervasiveness of data in these fields necessitates a familiarity with research data management, FAIR principles, cheminformatics and classic data science, which the Cookbook is well-positioned to support.

Figure 1. Diversity of Cookbook users, including a wide range of professionals and learners.

In terms of the practical environments of our users, we envisage engagement from commercial, academic, and educational institutions. Research and development units, such as librarians aiding researchers or scientists integrating machine-processing in their research, will find this resource particularly relevant. Data journal editors and repository curators in the publishing sector, as well as systems and software engineers managing chemical data, will also derive significant benefit from the breadth of guidance the Cookbook provides (see Figure 1).

2.3 Applicability in teaching chemists

For chemists, an understanding of the FAIR data principles is no longer ancillary; it is as vital as any other laboratory skill. It equips them to contribute to and leverage the collective knowledge base of the chemistry community, enhancing research productivity and enabling domain knowledge to grow exponentially. Students trained in FAIR principles can ensure their research outputs are accessible to collaborators and future scientists and also enhance their own reuse of available data, thereby accelerating the pace of scientific discovery.

The use of the Cookbook in an educational setting is pivotal for nurturing the next generation of chemists with competencies that extend beyond the bench. It provides a foundation for developing data skills crucial for a new breed of professionals: data stewards and curators. The cultivation of these roles is essential for the progression of chemistry as a discipline, ensuring that data is not only preserved but also primed for discovery and innovation. Educators employing the FAIR Chemistry Cookbook in their teaching will provide students and fellow scientists with more than just knowledge—they will be imparting a mindset attuned to the collaborative and cumulative nature of scientific endeavour in the digital age. This approach builds a community where data is shared openly, fostering an environment that encourages innovation and reproducible science.

As a first step to getting this important material into education, there is an urgent need to communicate with educators about how we in chemistry should understand and adapt to FAIR and its implications. With respect to this, a focal point of the evolution of the Cookbook is to provide the resources needed for educators to understand as well as to teach the content.¹⁷ It seems logical that courses could be developed around this topic and made widely available to the educational community.^{18, 19}

¹⁷ McEwen, L. & Mustafa, F. "WorldFAIR Chemistry: Making IUPAC Assets FAIR" *Chemistry International*, vol. 45, no. 1, (2023), pp. 14-17. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ci-2023-0104>

¹⁸ Shanahan, H., Hoebelheinrich, N., & Whyte, A. "Progress toward a comprehensive teaching approach to the FAIR data principles." *Patterns* 2.10 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100324>

¹⁹ Fink, F., Hoffmann, A. & Herres-Pawlis, S. "Results of a Three-Year Survey on the Implementation of Research Data Management and the Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN) Chemotion in an Advanced Inorganic Lab Course." *Journal of Chemical Education* 100.11 (2023): 4287-4297. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.3c00380>

3. IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook

This initiative aims to support teaching and training needs for managing and working with machine-readable FAIR chemical data through an openly-accessible collaborative resource that exemplifies the FAIR principles and standards in cheminformatics. The IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook is intended to be a self-serve web-based toolbox tailored to users with a basic level of competency in Python programming, digital data, and research data management. It is specifically designed for users who are knowledgeable in the basics yet have not attained advanced cheminformatics or data science expertise.

The twin goals are to get more practical tools and tips for handling machine-readable data into the hands of practising chemists and others working with chemical data; and to lower barriers and smooth the adoption of best practices for sharing and reusing FAIR chemical data. The underlying principles and objectives that drove the direction and development of the resource are described further below, followed by general descriptions of the infrastructure and processes involved in deploying, using and contributing to the Cookbook.

3.1 Conceptual development

The conceptual development of the Cookbook was aimed at creating a resource that was as dynamic and accessible as possible, in order to facilitate a long term view on teaching and training these principles. The ideas of ‘community-driven’, ‘flexible’ and ‘updateable’ were key themes in mind when planning the Cookbook. At its heart, our ambition is to produce a repository of interactive content that could evolve in real-time with the contributions of the community.

The idea behind developing a ‘cookbook’ was the need for a set of pseudo-formulaic processes that a bench chemist (or any non-expert in research data management and automated data handling) could deploy with minimal effort. We believe that efficiency is also a key value that needs to be embodied here, from both a learning and a deployment perspective. A user needs to be able to efficiently deploy the skills in the Cookbook to aid with their immediate problems, while the community and administrators need to be able to efficiently update the Cookbook to stay relevant.

The open-contribution model is a cornerstone of the design, fostering a collaborative environment that invites contributions from chemists, data scientists, educators, and students worldwide. This structure is not just about accumulating content; it is about embracing the collective expertise of the community to enhance the quality, diversity, and applicability of the Cookbook. The content is thus a living body of work, designed to grow and adapt as new contributions are made and as the field of cheminformatics evolves. This ensures that the resource remains relevant and continues to meet the community's needs for reliable, FAIR-enabled data practices.

To make it easy for IUPAC to provide ongoing support, all systems, procedures and processes to maintain the Cookbook have been designed to be as efficient as possible whilst being very well documented. Roles have been identified for administration and review within the core project as well as encouraging contribution from the broader community. This underscores the Cookbook's sustainability, and commitment to the resource's continuous improvement and longevity, and assures its evolution alongside advancements in chemical research and education.

3.2 Features and functionality

Jupyter Book emerged as the preferred platform choice for publishing the Cookbook based on the functionality needed for the project, existing knowledge in the project team and inspiration from the recent development of the ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook.²⁰ Jupyter Book offers a seamless blend of rich text for explanations and tutorials with executable code blocks—ideal for the Cookbook's hands-on, learn-by-doing approach.²¹ Deployment is administered via GitHub, providing all the necessary tools enabling the project to build a resource that fits with the overarching aims and ideals we hoped to embody.²²

Key features identified as essential in the development and ongoing maintenance of the Cookbook include:

- **Interactivity:** The use of Jupyter Book allows for interactive notebooks, which are crucial for subject matter where learning is significantly enhanced by doing. This feature empowers users to test, modify, and execute code directly in the Cookbook site, providing a hands-on experience that is integral to the learning process.
- **Community contributions:** Leveraging GitHub's collaborative features, the Cookbook is designed to encourage contributions from the community. Detailed documentation has been created to guide users on raising pull requests (PRs) to submit enhancements or new content, encouraging a constant stream of fresh and peer-reviewed material.
- **Quality assurance:** GitHub Actions²³ are configured to automate checks on submitted contributions, ensuring that any addition to the Cookbook meets the high standards required for educational content and code functionality.
- **Continuous deployment:** The integration of GitHub Actions also facilitates the automatic deployment of the Cookbook. As contributions are merged, the Jupyter Book on GitHub Pages is rebuilt, making the latest content immediately available to users.
- **Sustainability:** By hosting the Cookbook on GitHub and automating its deployment, the project ensures that the resource would be sustainable and easy to maintain in the long term, with minimal manual intervention required.

²⁰ ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook for Life Sciences, <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org>

²¹ Jupyter Book project, <https://jupyterbook.org>

²² GitHub Pages, <https://docs.github.com/en/pages/quickstart>

²³ <https://github.com/features/actions>

Interactive ‘recipes’ are developed with the intent to empower users to handle real-world chemical data scenarios effectively. The plug-and-play aspect is highly important, and requires code, instructions and data sets to be available and to be seamlessly integrated into the user's workflow. The advantages of this are many. It makes self-tuition a much easier experience, hopefully leading to more uptake of the technology and improved retention of knowledge. It improves the efficiency with which researchers can carry out their work as they can test recipes with their own data and calculate output automatically. The resource is also easier to manage as admins aren't reliant on third-party data or code that is outside of their control. These aspects all add to the overall functionality of the Cookbook, making a more seamless experience for community users and contributors.

By allowing community users to add content, the Cookbook taps into a wide array of experiences and perspectives. This inclusive approach ensures that the resource remains up-to-date with the latest advancements and challenges in the field of chemistry. Contributions might range from new recipes that address emerging research techniques to updates of existing content that reflect the latest best practices or regulatory changes. The process of contributing is structured to be as accessible as possible. Clear guidelines and templates are provided to ensure that submissions meet the Cookbook's standards for clarity, consistency, and alignment with FAIR principles. This guidance helps maintain a high quality of content while simplifying the contribution process for new users.

The benefits of this open-contribution model extend beyond content creation. It also encourages peer review and critique, leading to a more robust and reliable resource. Contributors can suggest improvements, report issues, or provide alternative approaches to problems, all of which enriches the learning experience for all users. Contributions and feedback are monitored by an editorial board of community members established within the project who have experience in cheminformatics and GitHub workflows. A consistent review process along with submission guidelines ensures that each submission provides educational value and is managed through sustainable mechanisms.

Moreover, the model encourages a sense of ownership and investment among contributors. When users offer their insights and expertise, they become stakeholders in the Cookbook's success, fostering a vested interest in its continued relevance and utility. This sense of community ownership is pivotal in driving the resource's evolution and ensuring it remains a valued tool for learning and discovery. This dynamic and democratic process ensures that the IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook remains a cutting-edge resource that adapts to the ever-changing landscape of chemical data management.

3.3 Content scope

Recipes are designed to exemplify the FAIR principles, demonstrating how chemical data should be managed, shared and curated for reuse. The aim is to present all materials with relevant chemistry examples, point to high-quality external resources where available, reference IUPAC and community digital standards where appropriate, and engage the chemistry community in order to broaden the understanding of enabling and exploiting FAIR data in chemistry. Initially, the user base is presumed to be well-positioned to implement the skills and have access to the required infrastructure. As such, the Cookbook serves as an introductory to intermediate guide, directing those who fall outside this skill bracket towards external resources for upskilling in preparation for the Cookbook's content – for example the NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base, the NanoCommons Handbook and the ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook.^{24, 25, 26}

The Cookbook provides a variety of protocols developed by active community members that target different tasks across a range of possible use cases for working with machine-readable chemical data (i.e., FAIR data). The scope of the Cookbook is quite broad and includes interactive content in the following categories:

- **Tools and web services**
Recipes in this section highlight online cheminformatics tools and web services that can help data researchers in the chemical sciences curate digital data. Material includes brief explanations, tutorials and demos of what can be done, and indicate scenarios where the tool might be used to manipulate machine-readable chemical data – both by humans and machines.
- **Data sources**
Recipes in this section review accessible online sources of reliable FAIR chemical data, including research data repositories and other aggregated sources. Materials include brief descriptions of content and available documentation, and provide tutorials and demos of API protocols for uploading, searching and retrieving various types of data.
- **Data manipulations**
Recipes in this section demonstrate atomised workflows for specific tasks related to managing and working with machine-readable chemical data. Interactive examples are included as demonstrations that can be copied and executed through a Jupyter Notebook or other Python-based code.

²⁴ NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base, https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base

²⁵ NanoCommons User Guidance HandBook, <https://nanocommons.github.io/user-handbook/>

²⁶ ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook for Life Sciences, <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org>

- **Use cases and workflows**

Entries in this section demonstrate the application of multiple workflow stages (tasks) to address specific use cases for preparing or reusing FAIR data. Recipes highlight various sequences of data curation and may refer to resources highlighted in other sections of the Cookbook or in other external resources.

The content is freely available and includes Jupyter Notebooks, spreadsheets, datasets, instruction sets, and plug-and-play executable code. Users can access and adapt these resources to fit their specific requirements. Most of the content in the Cookbook is licensed for reuse under CC BY or CC BY-SA 4.0 International,²⁷ or MIT-0²⁸ for code. Suggested citations are provided with the recipes, allowing users to reference content properly in their own work and scholarly communications. This is essential for the integration of the Cookbook's resources into academic and research contexts (as applicable) and demonstrates the Cookbook's commitment to practise what it preaches.

To facilitate use and discovery of its resources, the Cookbook provides descriptive metadata that details background context, content complexity, skills prerequisites and learning outcomes. This metadata ensures that users can efficiently identify the most relevant resources for their needs and is displayed prominently in a manner that will be understandable to the target audience (see Figure 2 below.)

²⁷ Creative Commons licences: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/list>

²⁸ MIT licence: <https://opensource.org/license/mit>

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the OPSIN website. The page title is "OPSIN: Open Parser for Systematic IUPAC Nomenclature". The left sidebar contains a navigation menu with sections like "Introduction", "The FAIR Chemistry Cookbook", "Tools & Web Services", and "Reference". The main content area features a heading "OPSIN: Open Parser for Systematic IUPAC Nomenclature" and a section titled "About this tool" which lists the author (Stuart Chalk), reviewer (Leah McEwen), function, format, input, outputs, usage instructions, publication, website, and API endpoint. Below this, there is a paragraph of text explaining the tool's purpose in working with chemical data.

OPSIN: Open Parser for Systematic IUPAC Nomenclature

About this tool

- Author: [Stuart Chalk](#)
- Reviewer: [Leah McEwen](#)
- Function: IUPAC chemical name to chemical identifier converter
- Format: Website form based queries and URL based API
- Input: IUPAC systematic chemical name
- Outputs: Standard InChI string, Standard InChIKey, SMILES, Chemical Markup Language (CML) XML, image (.png or .svg)
- Usage: [Instructions](#)
- Publication: <https://doi.org/10.1021/ci100384d>
- Website: <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk>
- Application Programming Interface (API): <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/>
 - Endpoint: Chemical Markup Language file .cml (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.cml>)
 - Endpoint: Standard InChI text file .stdinchi (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.stdinchi>)
 - Endpoint: Standard InChIKey text file .stdinchikey (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.stdinchikey>)
 - Endpoint: SMILES text file .smi (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.smi>)
 - Endpoint: JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) file .json (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.json>)
 - Endpoint: PNG Image file .png (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.png>)
 - Endpoint: SVG Image file .svg (e.g., <https://opsin.ch.cam.ac.uk/opsin/benzene.svg>)
- GitHub Repository: [dan2097/opsin](https://github.com/dan2097/opsin)
- Citations: 'OPSIN: Open Parser for Systematic IUPAC Nomenclature', IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook, <https://w3id.org/icc/IFCC001>
- Reuse: This resource is made available under a [CC-BY-4.0](#) license.

Working with chemical data you quickly realize there are many situations where you want to augment a dataset with chemical identifiers, however they are not easy to find. This case arises where the compound/ion/complex/alloy you searching on is not very common and thus not in general databases like PubChem, Common Chemistry, or UniChem.

(Figure 2A) Overview of the tool

(Figure 2B) Using the tool in Python

Figure 2. Example Cookbook “Tool/Web Service” recipes about the OPSIN tool, with the “About” metadata headers expanded. (A) Overview of the tool; (B) Using the tool in Python.

4. Cookbook infrastructure

Creation of an open resource for training chemical sciences users in FAIR-related best practices has many requirements for development of an impactful, sustainable, and FAIR product. The most important of these requirements include:

- Open and FAIR development and deployment
- Support for a diverse set of user personas
- Agile development and adaptation to user needs
- Community engagement for long term stability
- Documentation at user, contributor, reviewer, and administrator levels

As discussed above, the choice of Jupyter Book as the development environment enables each of these requirements at the content creation level. There are many options that can be considered for

the online deployment of the book content and the choice of GitHub improves support for the above criteria and enables others.

By using the Jupyter Book package to create the Cookbook, development can be accomplished using any computer system as it is based on the Python programming language which can be run on any OS. Content is generated locally and managed through a GitHub repository.²⁹ Publication of the website pages created from the source files can be hosted anywhere online, with GitHub as a preferred option. The infrastructure and workflow for publishing the Cookbook, combining Jupyter Book and GitHub, is shown in Figure 3, below.

The Cookbook infrastructure provides an open, free implementation that can be administered by multiple admins, allows for easy backups, transparent review and open community feedback. Technical development will evolve as the project matures and as we receive feedback from the user community.

Figure 3. Workflow for deployment of the Cookbook: Local files -> GitHub repo -> Cookbook website

4.1 Cookbook website

The Cookbook is an online book that aims to present a simple-to-navigate environment for teaching and learning via rich content. Jupyter Book is an open source software stack, developed by the ExecutableSoftware project³⁰, that is focused on “an international collaboration to build open source tools that facilitate publishing computational narratives using the Jupyter ecosystem.” Jupyter Book has been developed to enable “building beautiful, publication-quality books and

²⁹ Cookbook GitHub repository, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook>

³⁰ <https://executablebooks.org/en/latest/tools/#tools-jupyter-book>

documents from computational content.”³¹ As such, the software is designed to make the development of content easy, through development of Markdown files in a text editor and by enabling interactive pages through publication of Jupyter Notebooks, which engage readers by executing Python code in the browser that they can follow in real time.

For this Cookbook project, Jupyter Book is perfectly aligned with the goal of training the chemistry community in ways to improve how to make data, workflows, and services more FAIR. Providing recipes using Python (a well-developed language widely used in the scientific community) provides code examples of how to download, process, store, and publish data in FAIRer ways and reinforces best practices in coding.³² Thus, users with some familiarity of Python can implement recipe code immediately, and as a result may decide to write their own recipes to give back to the Cookbook.

Jupyter Book comes with configuration options to enable/disable the following features of the Cookbook website (all are currently enabled in the Cookbook):

- **Table of contents:**
A table of contents (ToC) for the Cookbook is provided on the left hand side of the site for overall navigation of the recipes and background pages. This functionality is built into Jupyter Book and administrators can easily update the ToC by editing the configuration file.
- **Page navigation:**
Navigation within pages is provided on the right hand side and is generated based on the headers used within the recipe content. Headers are linked via HTML anchors which makes it easy for users to navigate to specific sections of a recipe and provides link references to specific sections of a recipe. For example, the following link will direct to the specific section of the recipe illustrated above in Figure 2B:
https://iupac.github.io/WFChemCookbook/tools/opsin_api_jn.html#step-3-call-the-opsin-image-api
- **Toolbar:**
A toolbar is also built into every page of the Cookbook to provide quick access to additional functionality. A rocket icon provides access to Binder³³ and Google Colab³⁴, two online Jupyter Notebook environments allowing Cookbook content to be run interactively in the browser. Options are also provided to download recipe content either as Markdown (.md) or Jupyter Notebook (.ipynb) files, or in static PDF documents. Users can also connect to the GitHub repository to post comments from a specific recipe.

³¹ Executable Books community guide, <https://executablebooks.org/en/latest/tools/#tools-jupyter-book>

³² Style Guide for Python Code, <https://peps.python.org/pep-0008>

³³ Mybinder, <https://mybinder.org>

³⁴ Google Colaboratory, <https://colab.research.google.com>

- **References:**

Jupyter Book allows authors to provide both internal references via labels and external references via citations. Labels allow for the creation of specific target(s) within recipe(s) that can be referred to in other recipes. Citations provide references to external resources through aggregation of bibliographic metadata in a bibtex ‘.bib’ file and subsequent citation using the cite ‘role’. The Cookbook is configured to automatically include a bibliography in each page where a recipe has a citation and to add the cumulative bibliography appearing at the bottom of the ToC.

It should also be noted that the implementation of the Cookbook via Jupyter Book and the companion GitHub repository from which it is published allows the project to be FAIR by making both the original content (.md, .ipynb, and config files) available (in the repository), alongside the Cookbook website (derived HTML content). Interested users can review the original content files, download the repository to their local computer and deploy the Cookbook on a local server if they have resources to do so.

4.2 GitHub repository

Publication of the Cookbook project files is enabled by syncing new content updates to the project GitHub repository. While originally developed for collaborative code development, GitHub has a feature set that supports the development of the Cookbook in addition to web hosting. The collaborative and open nature of a public GitHub repository is a perfect fit for the initial and ongoing development of the Cookbook. This is extremely important to the ongoing expansion of the content, capture of content reviews, bug reporting and documentation.

Recipes are organised in folders that align with the category of resource where they appear in the Cookbook, including tools, data sources, data manipulations, and use cases. In each category, a subpage represents a Cookbook resource, a Markdown file or Jupyter Notebook that describes specific training material relative to enabling chemical data and/or workflows more FAIR. Other files associated with the Cookbook such as images or sample datasets are organised by file types. This structure has been developed to make it easy to publish new recipes to the Cookbook.

Review and deployment of community contributions is managed and documented through the GitHub pull request system, used in code development for submission of new features. The contribution and review processes are further described in Section 5 of this report. Specific steps for preparing and contributing recipes are outlined in the GitHub repository wiki for the Cookbook, along with criteria for content and format requirements, and guidance on creating Markdown and Jupyter Notebook files (see Figure 4).³⁵

³⁵ GitHub repository wiki, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki>

Figure 4. Wiki for Cookbook contributors on how to develop recipe content.

GitHub issues³⁶ are configured for users to submit messages about errors, software not working, or other topics related to the Cookbook or GitHub repository. Nine templates are available for users to pick from that fit the types of questions anticipated (see Figure 5), including: bug reports, content or feature suggestions, notebooks, data sets or other contributions, reviews and other general feedback.

³⁶ GitHub issue templates, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/issues>

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for 'IUPAC / WFChemCookbook'. The 'Issues' tab is selected, showing a list of issue templates. Each template includes a title, a brief description, and a 'Get started' button.

Issue Type	Description	Action
Bug report	Create a report to help us improve the Cookbook	Get started
Content suggestion	Suggest an idea for the Cookbook project	Get started
Cookbook Contribution	Submit a contribution to the IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook project	Get started
Data Issue	Report errors or suggest improvements in the data being used in the examples	Get started
Documentation Issue	Report issues or suggest improvements to Cookbook documentation	Get started
Feature request	Suggest a new feature for the Cookbook project	Get started
General Feedback	Provide general observations and suggestions about the Cookbook project	Get started
Notebook Issue	Report issues or suggest improvements to a Jupyter notebook (executable code examples)	Get started
Submit a Review	This issue type is for reviewers of content to submit their review	Get started

Figure 5. Templates available to provide feedback in GitHub.

4.3 Technical deployment

Original instantiation of the Cookbook using the Jupyter Book Python package was done on a local machine using a number of pieces of software which support Python. After development of the original content, the project files are used to create a new repository on GitHub. The Cookbook website was subsequently deployed using GitHub pages through processing of the Markdown and Jupyter Notebooks files (into HTML), via the Jupyter Book package. The layout of the website is defined by the standard Jupyter Book organisation of page layout³⁷ which includes a left side table of contents, main content in the middle and current page navigation on the right side as described for the Cookbook website above. Further details on the technical setup are provided in Appendix 8.3 for any who may be interested in deploying Jupyter Books.

Subsequent updates are initiated when reviewers accept a new contribution into the Cookbook, via the PR mechanism. Files for a new recipe are downloaded from the GitHub repository for a final check before a link to the new recipe is added to the table of contents configuration file. The table of contents update and any modifications to the contribution files are then committed and pushed to GitHub. The new recipe is then published to the Cookbook via the automated GitHub action that is triggered by a push to the repository.

The Cookbook was initially published as a ‘sampler’ with a selection of content to test the model and deployment. Several additional services have been implemented to support ongoing maintenance of the site and evaluate future impact of the Cookbook, including:

- **Automation of the maintenance of the content:**
Updating the content was moved to the project GitHub repository, by implementing a GitHub ‘action’ to create the HTML pages and subsequently publish them.³⁸ The action runs whenever new content is pushed to the main branch of the repository.
- **Content link checking:**
In order to make sure that links work throughout the Cookbook, and especially after the addition of new recipes, the open source Python package ‘linkchecker’ is run to provide recursive checks each time the Cookbook is updated.³⁹
- **Cookbook analytics using Matomo:**
Matomo Analytics⁴⁰ is an open-source tool that, akin to Google Analytics, will allow us to monitor traffic on the Cookbook website. Matomo is used by many organisations, including the European Union.

³⁷ Jupyter Book content layout, <https://jupyterbook.org/en/stable/content/layout.html>

³⁸ GitHub deployment action, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/blob/main/.github/workflows/deploy.yml>

³⁹ GitHub linkchecker, <https://github.com/linkchecker/linkchecker>

⁴⁰ Matomo Analytics, <https://matomo.org/>

A separate (private) administrative GitHub repository⁴¹ has been developed to support the ongoing development of the website and GitHub repository. This repository contains documentation of how to administer the infrastructure of the project, describes specific decisions over the course of iterative development, provides rationale and how-to, and captures important security-related information. This material will be used to train future administrators and allow institutional knowledge to be passed down generations of admins.

5. Contribution pipeline

A major activity within the development of the Cookbook has been to anticipate the future development of the Cookbook and define a process by which members of the community can contribute to the content in an open and FAIR manner. This is advantageous for increasing the breadth of content and as a mechanism to create an active community around the Cookbook that will enable its ongoing development and increase awareness of the resource generally.

Contributions to the Cookbook are administered through the GitHub repository using pull requests (PRs). This involves an open submission and review process that exemplifies FAIR practices and provides contributors with trackable credit for their submission. The setup and processes for supporting community contribution of recipes are further described in the following sections and in the GitHub repository wiki⁴². The approach will continue to be refined as the Cookbook project evolves.

5.1 Content preparation

Content for the Cookbook is submitted either as Markdown (.md) files for background articles or Jupyter Notebook (.ipynb) for recipes with executable code. Markdown files are text files and can be written in any text editor using a syntax that allows the content to be easily converted in HTML. Jupyter Notebook files are Python files that require a knowledge of Python to develop. Tips for creating Markdown files and Jupyter Notebooks are described in the wiki.

Contributions to the Cookbook must contain at least one Markdown or Jupyter Notebook file and can also include additional files such as images or videos, as well as other text-based files such as spreadsheets. Each recipe needs to include an embedded metadata section that describes attributes about the resource or task demonstrated; for example: prior skills, learning outcomes, how to cite the recipe, reuse licence, etc.

All files needed for a Cookbook contribution are organised into a contribution folder using a specified folder structure and file-naming conventions as described in the wiki. This ensures that all files from one contribution can be easily identified and archived and moving accepted contributions

⁴¹ <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook-Admin/>

⁴² <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki>

into the Cookbook is standardised, documented and managed on an ongoing basis. Contributors can submit recipes through either a PR or a “Contribution Issue” using a specific template. Specific steps for each method are outlined in the wiki.⁴³

5.2 Editorial process

All new contributions to the Cookbook are reviewed by members of the current project who have experience with cheminformatics and are knowledgeable about GitHub workflows and best practices. The review is conducted on the GitHub repository through an open dialogue between contributor and reviewer. Review is enabled through the PR process and admins can request edits and merge the updates into the main branch of the Cookbook.

At least two reviewers are assigned to a contribution; however, only one approved review is needed for the contribution to be accepted. Reviewers assigned to a submission review the content for conformance to the submission criteria, formatting of files, organisation and naming of contribution folder and included files, appropriateness of content, alignment with best practices in coding, clarity of the narrative, and complementarity to existing content. If a contribution is generally acceptable, reviewers will give feedback to contributors on any changes needed for final acceptance of the contribution and these can be submitted as part of the PR. Once accepted for inclusion, each contribution is assigned a permanent identifier and the content moved to the appropriate category for addition to the Cookbook.

Reviewer guidelines are documented on the wiki and will continue to be updated as the review process is further refined.⁴⁴ The project will continue to expand the reviewer pool and optimise the expected workload and timeframe for reviewers. There is also interest in contributions in other programming languages, which will also require knowledgeable reviewers.

5.3 Unique identifiers for recipes

To facilitate citation and reuse, each of the contributed resources to the Cookbook is assigned a resolvable unique identifier. Two options were considered for this project: Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)⁴⁵ and World Wide Web Permanent Identifiers (W3IDs)⁴⁶. W3IDs were selected as they are being used by the ELIXIR FAIR Cookbook, and are free to use and easier to manage than DOIs. The revision history of the recipe files are available in the GitHub repository to track specific versions. This decision may be revisited as the Cookbook evolves depending on the needs of the community.

Recipes can be cited using the W3ID according to the following syntax:

⁴³ Wiki, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki/How-to-submit-a-contribution-to-the-Cookbook>

⁴⁴ Wiki, <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki/Reviewer-Guidelines>

⁴⁵ Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), <https://www.doi.org/>

⁴⁶ World Wide Web Permanent Identifiers (W3IDs), <https://w3id.org/>

<Authors: Last name, first initial.> “<Recipe Title>”, IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook.
Contributed: YYYY-MM-DD. <W3ID URL>.

6. Community engagement

Through the Cookbook, chemists, researchers, educators, and practitioners can access a repository of knowledge that is not static but grows richer with each contribution. It is a testament to what can be achieved when a community comes together to share, learn, and build upon each other's work. This collaborative platform is not just about individual gains but also about collective advancement, where the shared goal is to enhance research and teaching across disciplines through the FAIR principles. The Cookbook is intended to become more than a collection of resources; it's a dynamic platform that invites community participation.

6.1 Using the Cookbook

The IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook is a curated open resource tailored to users with a basic level of competency in Python programming, digital data, and research data management. It is specifically designed for users who are knowledgeable in the basics yet have not attained advanced cheminformatics or data science expertise. Users may also wish to refer to additional community resources for background on FAIR data management; for example, the NFDI4Chem knowledge base⁴⁷.

The Cookbook presents a collection of annotated code snippets and demonstration workflows for using online tools and executing common tasks in annotating and managing digital chemical data and metadata.

- Many of the recipes on this site take advantage of Jupyter Notebooks to run Python code in the browser for an interactive (and educational) feel for the user.
- Information on how, what and when a recipe might be useful is available in the collapsable 'header' below the title of the recipe.
- The header also includes bullets for skills and learning objectives.
- The content is available for reuse under CC BY or CC BY-SA 4.0 International.
- Users are encouraged cite their use of any recipes from the Cookbook; for example: Chalk, S. “Accessing the IUPAC Gold Book API in Python”, IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook. Contributed: 2023-02-28. <https://w3id.org/ifcc/IFCC003>
- Ideas from users on additional resources to demonstrate and using recipes in data management workflows and teaching materials are welcome: bit.ly/CbookFeedback⁴⁸.

⁴⁷ NFDI4Chem Knowledge Base, https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base

⁴⁸ Cookbook feedback, bit.ly/CbookFeedback

In the educational context, the Cookbook could help spark a revolution in the education of the chemistry community toward data science at many levels. Some contributors are already planning additional recipes that can be reused in teaching and training, as well as more broadly. Jupyter Book is becoming an established tool in many educational settings⁴⁹ and we expect to see derivations of the Cookbook adapted for specific class scenarios in chemistry to address the need in data science education.

In a course taught by the project lead on "Chemical Information Science", students are learning a range of skills for organising and managing digital data programmatically online, including: what chemical identifiers and representations are, how relational databases are set up, how to access data repository APIs, and how to manage data in machine-readable forms such as bringing chemical data back into Python as JSON. Many of these activities could be developed into individual recipes and contributed into the Cookbook for use in other classes in various combinations.

Skills developed by the students throughout the class are then applied to a final project to create a web application framework, using open source tools, that enables students to curate data from the literature. This process allows students to understand how all these data-handling topics play into making chemistry data more digitally FAIR and available to the community. Students in previous iterations of this class have often commented that they now have a very different view on data, and how they appreciate the efforts of those behind large data repositories.

6.1.1 Worked example: Structured UV/Vis (meta)data for small molecule characterisation

This workflow recipe, "Structured UV/Vis (meta)data for small molecule characterisation"⁵⁰, describes how to format data and metadata associated with a specific chemical data type (ultraviolet/visible or UV/Vis spectrum) to submit as supplementary information to a journal article, and demonstrates how these data can then be reused for further property analysis⁵¹. The demonstration in this recipe (see Figures 6-10 below) uses an openly-available dataset from the NIST Chemistry WebBook⁵², and Cookbook users can also run this recipe with other files of the same type. Screenshots of the recipe are used to illustrate the overall sequence of the workflow as it is laid out in the Cookbook; interested readers are encouraged to go directly to the recipe online to follow along in real time.

⁴⁹ Jupyter Book gallery, <https://executablebooks.org/en/latest/gallery>

⁵⁰ <https://w3id.org/ifcc/IFCC010>

⁵¹ Bloodworth, S., Coles, S., Monday, S. "Structured UV/Vis (meta)data for small molecule characterisation", IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook, Contributed: 2023-02-28 <https://w3id.org/ifcc/IFCC010>

⁵² <https://webbook.nist.gov/>

Figure 6. *The Structured UV/Vis (meta)data recipe*

Structuring the (meta)data

The recipe starts out by reviewing standard / best practice text-based file formats for storing the data and metadata so that they can be imported into other software (e.g., Excel) and enable the user to plot the spectral data. Users can identify different file types to record and process sample identification, substance representation, and important contextual parameters related to the spectrum (see Figure 7 below).

3.2 File hierarchy

Content	Definition	Priority	Format
Raw Data			
Data matrix (with or without column headings)	Spectrophotometer output as tabular data (absorbance and wavelength)	Essential	CSV (.csv) JCAMP-DX (.jdx)
Sample level metadata			
Sample ID	Identifier for the sample which is unique within the project	Essential	Plain text (.txt) XML (.xml)
Linking sample ID	Provenance identifier for the sample in the associated process capture document (digital or paper notebook)	Essential	R Markdown (.rmd) Jupyter Notebook Markdown (.ipynb)
Data labels (if absent from the data matrix)	Description and units for the tabular raw data columns	Essential	
Sample concentration, solvent, optical path length, user ID and date/time of collection	Experimental parameters	Essential	
Chemical structure	Chemical structure identifier in the form of an alphanumeric text string	Essential	InChI SMILES
	SMILES validation	Desirable	Toolkit(version) identifier
Analysis level metadata			
Processed data matrix	Tabular data: absorbance, wavelength, and molar absorptivity (ϵ); with data labels and units	Essential	CSV (.csv)
Data reporting:	The two key outputs required for publication.	Essential	R Markdown (.rmd) Jupyter Notebook Markdown (.ipynb)
Project level metadata			
Study ID	Identifier(s) for the scientific study	Desirable	Plain text (.txt)

Figure 7. Metadata useful for contextualising spectral data and file formats for storage.

Data preparation using Jupyter Notebook package for Python

The recipe then describes the Jupyter Notebook file that was developed to demonstrate how Python code can be used to work with the standard data files (IUPAC standard JCAMP-DX format in this case). Users are guided through installation of packages to read the data file and subsequently display the spectrum in the browser (see Figure 8). Users can then execute the code by launching the Jupyter Notebook into Binder (see Figure 9) or Google Colab.

Figure 8. Python code reading and displaying the contents of a JCAMP-DX file.

Figure 9. Python code displaying the spectrum contained in the JCAMP-DX file.

Using the data

After the user has seen how Python can be used to ingest the data file and create a plot, the final blocks of Python code demonstrate how to set up an analysis sequence. The recipe walks through how to extract the wavelength of maximum absorbance and the absorbance at that wavelength, and then use a documented Python function (“def”) to calculate the molar absorptivity of the molecule - an important metric about the relative absorption of ultraviolet/visible light (see Figure 10).


```

381.6 nm
1577.0 L mol-1 cm-1

Now we create a function to apply the Beer Lambert law to convert Absorbance (A) to Absorptivity (ε) followed by a line of code to run the function.

In [9]: # noinspection PyShadowingNames
def beer_lambert(absorbance, concentration, length):
    """
    Doc String

    Calculates the molar absorptivity (epsilon) using the Beer-Lambert Law.

    The Beer-Lambert Law states that the absorbance (Absorbance) of a solution is directly proportional
    to the concentration (concentration) of the absorbing species and the path length (length) of the
    light through the solution.

    Parameters:

        absorbance (float): The measured absorbance of the solution
        concentration (float): The concentration of the absorbing species in the solution, in molar
        length (float): The path length of the light through the solution, in cm.

    Returns:

        epsilon (float): The molar absorptivity of the solution.

    """
    epsilon = absorbance/(concentration*length)
    return epsilon

absorbance = 1 # Edit to your own value
concentration = 2 # Edit to your own value
length = 3 # Edit to your own value

epsilon = beer_lambert(absorbance, concentration, length) # Replace each of the parameters, absorbance,
# concentration and length with your own numbers.

print(f'The molar absorptivity (ε) is: {epsilon:.3f} L mol-1 cm-1')
The molar absorptivity (ε) is: 0.167 L mol-1 cm-1

```

Figure 10. Python code calculating important spectral characteristics.

6.2 Contributing to the Cookbook

The Cookbook's structure is designed to harness the collective intelligence of the chemical data community. As contributors add their unique content, they enhance the Cookbook's breadth by covering a broader range of topics and its depth by providing detailed, expert insights into specific areas. The Cookbook's content is a living body of work, designed to grow and adapt as new contributions are made and as the field of cheminformatics evolves. This ensures that the resource remains relevant and continues to meet the community's needs for reliable, FAIR-enabled data practices.

To encourage the community to contribute to the Cookbook, the documentation wiki⁵³ on the project GitHub website details, in the following sections, how to prepare and submit new recipes:

- [What is the IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook?](#)
- [How was the Cookbook developed?](#)
- [How to create content for the Cookbook](#)
- [How to submit a contribution to the Cookbook](#)
- [Benefits of contributing to the Cookbook](#)

Contributors can submit recipes by one of two mechanisms:

- Submitting a [Pull Request](#) to the Cookbook GitHub Repository
- Submitting a [Contribution Issue](#) to the GitHub Repository

The project welcomes suggestions for recipes that showcase preparing and working with FAIR machine-readable chemical data in the following areas:

- Data sources: Data that can be openly accessed, either to supplement research data or integrate with research data (aggregate analyses).
- Tools and web services: Tools you can use to help you be more FAIR. These can be programs/packages installed on your computer or web-based services.
- Data manipulations: Atomised workflows for specific tasks related to managing machine-readable chemical data.
- Use cases and workflows: Multiple stage (tasks) workflows to address specific use cases for preparing or reusing FAIR data.

As the content of the Cookbook will be defined by the community, the resource will be instrumental in helping the chemistry community determine what criteria define FAIR data, what chemical data science really is, and at what level different topics need to be appropriately introduced to students and practitioners at large. As the resource grows, we will start to see different facets of the discipline and areas of application emerge, and in turn further understand how and where this material is important to address in chemical research and the greater enterprise.

6.3 Further outreach and collaboration

The IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook represents what we hope will become a focal point of expertise in the field of research data management, FAIR data, cheminformatics and classic data science. It is designed to be a living resource that adapts to the evolving landscape of chemistry. It also has the potential to actively shape this landscape by embodying a vision for a more open, accessible, and interconnected scientific community.

⁵³ <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki>

Realising this vision will require a continuing programme of outreach, content expansion and ongoing collaboration with data initiatives in the chemical and adjacent sciences including NFDI4Chem,⁵⁴ PSDI: Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure⁵⁵ and PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals.⁵⁶ Several additional recipes are already in the review pipeline and many more in conceptual stages from active project members and collaborators.

IUPAC is perfectly positioned to expand awareness through a strong international community of educators in the Committee on Chemical Education⁵⁷ and the union's education journal, *Chemistry Teacher International*⁵⁸, and planning is underway for a follow up project to develop 'train the trainers' materials to familiarise educators with use of the Cookbook in teaching.

Outreach materials developed in the project to date are listed in Appendix 8.2 and a broader promotion package for the Cookbook has been initiated. A development plan for ongoing sustainability, outlining anticipated contributions and collaborations, a community survey and other marketing and outreach is being elaborated over the remaining period of the WorldFAIR project as part of the IUPAC Roadmap for Sustainable Standards Development.

7. Conclusion

The IUPAC FAIR Chemistry Cookbook embodies the concepts we hope to impart to the chemistry community. The Cookbook functions as a practical implementation of the FAIR principles, providing a framework that can be replicated for the development of other educational materials. The Cookbook's architecture, built upon the ideals of community, automation, and interactivity, not only serves its immediate educational purpose but also sets a platform for the next iteration of materials. It is a resource that not only delivers information but also fosters a collaborative culture that is vital for the progression of the chemical sciences in the digital era.

In the evolving landscape of chemical research and education, the Cookbook has the potential to act as a critical resource to bridge a notable gap in the current educational frameworks for chemists. It is supremely flexible, easily updatable and community-driven, all assets to help it both target the right user groups and remain relevant in an environment where the skills needed in the workforce will constantly be changing. The resource is poised to be dynamic, with the range of material growing in variety and utility as the community contributes further, thus potentially broadening the spectrum of users over time. With a focus on the application of the FAIR principles, the Cookbook is anticipated to be a valuable asset to those already versed in these areas, as well as to those for

⁵⁴ NFDI4Chem, <https://www.nfdi4chem.de>

⁵⁵ PSDI: Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure, <https://www.psdi.ac.uk>

⁵⁶ PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals, <https://www.eu-parc.eu>

⁵⁷ IUPAC Committee on Chemical Education, <https://iupac.org/body/050>

⁵⁸ *Chemistry Teacher International*, <https://www.degruyter.com/journal/key/cti/html>

whom these concepts are new yet essential to their professional development, serving as both an educational tool and a best-practice guide for data stewardship.

In summary, the Cookbook is not merely a tool by which a user can upskill. By using this resource, the goal is for users to be empowered to make significant strides in their work, ensuring they are not just consumers of information but active contributors to the ever-expanding universe of chemical data. Ultimately, the Cookbook is envisioned as an indispensable tool for a targeted yet diverse audience, fulfilling unique needs that intersect at the junction of chemical data management and FAIR principles.

8. Appendices

8.1 Project contributors

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8.2 Outreach activities

- **Oral presentation: ‘Digital recipes for managing chemical data (Cookbook)’⁵⁹.**
This is an overview of the WorldFAIR Chemistry⁶⁰ sub-project, ‘Training Cookbook’⁶¹. It was presented at the workshop ‘Advancing FAIR Chemistry: Developing New Services for Sharing Chemical Data’, which took place during the ACS spring meeting in Indianapolis, USA, on 27 March, 2023.⁶²
- **Poster presentation: IUPAC WorldFAIR Chemistry: Managing Chemical Data Digitally.**
WorldFAIR Chemistry poster presented at the IUPAC CHAINS. The meeting took place in the Hague, the Netherlands, 18-26 August, 2023.⁶³

⁵⁹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7803867>

⁶⁰ <https://worldfair-project.eu/chemistry-wp3/>

⁶¹ <https://iupac.org/project/2022-028-1-024/>

⁶² Chalk, S. (2023). Digital recipes for managing chemical data (Cookbook). Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7803867>

⁶³ Mustafa, F., McEwen, L., Bruno, I., Chalk, S., & Bolton, E. (2023). IUPAC WorldFAIR Chemistry: Managing Chemical Data Digitally. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8322967>

- **Video: Cookbook website demo.**
View a video of the Cookbook demo [here](#)⁶⁴. Explore the Cookbook [here](#)⁶⁵. Feedback is welcomed via the [questionnaire](#)⁶⁶.

8.3 Implementation and deployment of the Cookbook technology

Instantiation of a project using the Jupyter Book Python package can be done on a desktop computer using a number of pieces of software which support Python. Equally, the software should support creation of Markdown pages (.md files) and the development of Jupyter notebooks (.ipynb files) which add interactivity to content that is afforded by online services like Binder⁶⁷ and Google Colab⁶⁸. The initial development of the Cookbook project was authored using the JetBrains Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for Python called PyCharm, one of many options available on both macOS and Windows.

***Note:** In the following description it is assumed that a developer has installed a recent version of Python (e.g [Python 3.11](#)), all necessary [Python packages](#) such as 'Jupyter book', 'pipenv', and 'pip' (or other preferred options), and the version control software '[git](#)'. All this software is available for free at the links provided.*

Creation of the project and addition of content is followed by the creation of HTML files from the Markdown and Jupyter notebook files. Creation of the HTML is done on the desktop using the following command line statement, a command to run the build action in the Jupyter book Python package, which creates the HTML content in the 'book' directory.

```
jupyter-book build book/
```

Subsequent deployment of the Cookbook project website (HTML pages) is enabled by integration of the project with GitHub and the installation of another Python package, [GitHub Pages Import](#) (GPI). (Note: This is outlined in the [Jupyter book documentation](#).) To move the project content to GitHub the local project is first enabled for version control using the free [git version control system](#) (VCS) software. At this point the git versioned project files can be uploaded to GitHub as a repository, in this case under the [IUPAC organisation account](#) using an initial commit. Secondly, the developer updates the settings on the GitHub repository to use [GitHub pages](#) (steps 3 - 8) and the GPI package is used to move the HTML pages to the GitHub Pages branch of the repository (making them

⁶⁴ Chalk, S. (2023). Where can I get help to manage chemical data FAIRly?.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=i37grSzWeAI>

⁶⁵ bit.ly/CookFAIR

⁶⁶ bit.ly/CbookFeedback

⁶⁷ <https://mybinder.org>

⁶⁸ <https://colab.research.google.com>

available at <https://<organization name>.github.io/<reponame>/>) using the command line statement:

```
ghp-import -n -p -f book/_build/html
```


Figure 11. a GitHub ‘action’ (script) added to the GitHub repository to allow automatic uploading to the Cookbook website.

The process above was used to publish the Cookbook website (or update the site) while it was in development. However, while the process does work, it is not a sustainable solution as it requires the project lead to publish all changes for the Cookbook. To allow all project admins to update the

Cookbook, a GitHub ‘action’ (script) was developed (based on the [example in Jupyter Book](#)⁶⁹) and added to the GitHub repository (Figure 11). This action fires every time file updates are ‘committed’ to the project repository, causing the Cookbook HTML files to be recreated and then uploaded automatically to the GitHub pages repository branch – the Cookbook website.

8.3.1 The Cookbook website

The Cookbook website is deployed using GitHub pages, a special branch of GitHub repositories that needs to be enabled to use. As shown above, the content is derived from markdown files and Jupyter Notebooks which are converted to HTML pages, with Jupyter Book (via Sphinx) taking care of the HTML formatting.

Training material in the Cookbook is presented using cooking as the analogy. This has been used to allow readers of the Cookbook to understand each of the different types of training content. The layout of the website is defined by the standard Jupyter Book [organisation of content](#), which includes a left side table of contents, main content in the middle and current page navigation on the right side. Page navigation is based on Markdown headers in both Markdown and Jupyter Notebook files.

Jupyter Book uses YAML files for configuration of a deployed book. Yet Another Markup Language ([YAML](#)) files (.yml) are basic text files that use space indentation to represent data that have a hierarchical structure. Preferences for the design and implementation of the book being developed are defined in the `_config.yml` file. This file also includes some configuration options for the [Sphinx Python package](#), which is used by Jupyter Book to implement the conversion of Markdown files to HTML.

In addition, the left side content is defined by the Jupyter Book `_toc.yml` file. Jupyter Book defines a set of data names for use in the YAML file to organise pages and subpages to the author’s specification. For the Cookbook, categories of content are stored in name folders, with introductory descriptions of each category as Markdown files with the same name as the folder. To make it easy to add new recipe contributions (no update to the `_toc.yml` file needed), all content found in a folder is assumed to be subpages of that category and this is defined by using a ‘glob’ field and the ‘*’ wildcard character; for example:

```
- file: tools
  title: Tools & Web Services
  sections:
    - glob: tools/*
```

⁶⁹ <https://jupyterbook.org/en/stable/publish/gh-pages.html#automatically-host-your-book-with-github-actions>

Here, 'file' defines the category and 'sections' defines all the subpages of that category. The 'glob' instruction indicates that any file in the 'tools' folder should be added as a subpage in the category.

In each category a subpage is a Cookbook resource, a Markdown file or Jupyter Notebook that describes specific training material about making chemical data and/or workflows more FAIR. Each resource page has an embedded metadata section that describes attributes about the resource including: topics, prior skills, learning outcomes, how to cite the resource and a reuse licence. Most of the content is licensed for reuse under CC BY or CC BY-SA 4.0 International.

In addition to resource content pages there are special folders for storing files associated with the Cookbook - the static folder contains website image and JavaScript files - and individual resource files. The structure has been developed to make it easy to add a new resource to the Cookbook once it has passed review.

8.3.2 The Cookbook GitHub repository

As mentioned previously, publication of the Cookbook project files is enabled by syncing new content updates to the project GitHub repository. While originally developed for collaborative code development, GitHub has a feature set that supports the development of the Cookbook in many ways, in addition to web hosting. The Jupyter Book documentation points out that publication of the HTML pages created from the Markdown and Jupyter Notebook files can be hosted anywhere online. The examples use GitHub as it is a preferred option.

The collaborative and open nature of a public GitHub repository is a perfect fit for the initial and ongoing development of the Cookbook. In the development to date we have taken advantage of many features of the GitHub website that allow a community to be built around the Cookbook. This is extremely important to the ongoing expansion of the content, capture of content reviews, bug reporting and documentation.

8.3.3 GitHub issue templates

GitHub issues are a means by which users of the repository content can submit messages about errors, software not working, or another other topic related to the repository. Many repositories customise the format of submitted issues by writing issue templates in accordance with GitHub's guidelines. For the Cookbook we have developed nine templates for users to pick from that fit the types of questions we expect (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. GitHub Issue Templates included to match user needs

As can be seen in Figure 13, issue templates are Markdown files [formatted in a specific structure](#) and placed in a 'ISSUE_TEMPLATE' folder inside the .github folder of the repository. This means they can be updated as needed by an admin just like any other file in the repository.

Figure 13. Issue templates are Markdown files formatted in a specific structure and placed in a 'ISSUE_TEMPLATE' folder inside the .github folder of the repository.

Subsequent development of the Cookbook infrastructure revolved around the following activities:

- **Developing a contribution pipeline:** The development of the Cookbook will be managed by IUPAC once the WorldFAIR project has ended. In order to continually improve and expand the content in the Cookbook it was critical that we develop a process for members of the community to submit contributions in an open and fair manner. Thus, it was decided to

create documentation (described below) and a process by which new content can be added. To implement this we:

- Configured the main branch of the GitHub repository with a 'Branch protection rule' that forced addition of new content to come through the Pull Request (PR) process.
- Require recipe submissions via the PR process, either by:
 - Forking the Cookbook repository, creating new content and submitting the new recipe as a PR from the forked repository; or
 - Creating a recipe, attaching the file(s) to a GitHub issue template, submitting the issue and working with a Cookbook admin to add a PR to the Cookbook repository (which then gets linked to the submitted issue).
- Enabled review of all content through the PR process
- Require approval by at least one of the repository maintainers.
- Automation of the maintenance of the content: Updating the content was moved to the project GitHub repository, by implementing a GitHub 'action' to create the HTML pages and subsequently publish them. The action can be found here⁷⁰ and runs whenever new content is pushed to the main branch of the repository.
- Publishing contribution documentation: This was added to the wiki section of the GitHub repository⁷¹ so that it is separate from user documentation of the Cookbook website and the administrator documentation.
- Development of a contribution structure and naming guidelines: To organise contributions, a folder structure and file naming conventions were developed so that:
 - All files from one contribution can be easily identified and archived
 - Moving accepted contribution content into the Cookbook is standardised, and thus easily documented.

This development was also aligned with the content categories (see above) of the Cookbook and the Jupyter Book table of contents configuration file (`_toc.yml`) used in creation of the book HTML. As a result, moving the files of a new contribution to the correct folders (in accordance with the standard administrator procedure) and committing and pushing the content to the main branch, results in the new contribution being published.

- Content link checking: This was implemented using the open source Python package 'linkchecker'⁷² on the command line. Installation of linkchecker is done using the command 'pip3 install linkchecker' and run linkchecker with the command 'linkchecker <https://iupac.github.io/WFChemCookbook/>' .
- Cookbook analytics using Matomo: The free Matomo software⁷³ was installed on an IUPAC-owned server and configured to monitor the Cookbook website. This was

⁷⁰ <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/blob/main/.github/workflows/deploy.yml>

⁷¹ <https://github.com/IUPAC/WFChemCookbook/wiki>

⁷² <https://github.com/linkchecker/linkchecker>

⁷³ <https://matomo.org/>

accomplished by adding a Matomo JavaScript file containing the tracking JavaScript to the Cookbook and updating the Jupyter book configuration file.

- Unique Identifiers for the Cookbook resources: Each of the contributed recipes to the Cookbook will obtain a resolvable unique identifier. Two options were considered for this: Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) and W3ID Permanent Identifiers (W3IDs). We decided to go with W3IDs as i) they are being used in the [FAIR Cookbook](#) project and ii) they are free to use and easier to manage the DOIs. This decision will be revisited as the Cookbook evolves.

Implementation of the W3IDs was done in accordance with the guidelines published on the groups' website.⁷⁴ Currently the project lead is in charge of the fork of the w3id repository, however this can easily moved to other admins if needed.

⁷⁴ W3 Identifiers, <https://w3id.org/#new>

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